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LOCAL REGION PSEUDO-ZERNIKE MOMENT- BASED FEATURE EXTRACTION FOR FACIAL RECOGNITION OF IDENTICAL TWINS

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ABSTRACT

In the domain of image processing, face recognition is one of the most well-known research field. When humans have very similar biometric properties, such as identical twins, the face recognition system is considered as a challengeable problem. In this paper, the AdaBoost method is utilized to detect the facial area of input image. After that the facial area is divided into some local regions. Finally, new efficient facial-based identical twins feature extractor based on the geometric moment is applied into local regions of face image. The used feature extractor is Pseudo-Zernike Moment (PZM) which is employed inside the local regions of facial area of identical twins images. To evaluate the proposed method, two datasets, Twins Days Festival and Iranian Twin Society, are collected where the datasets includes scaled and rotated facial images of identical twins in different illuminations. The experimental results demonstrates the ability of proposed method to recognize a pair of identical twins in different situations such as rotation, scaling and changing illumination

KEYWORDS

Face Recognition, Local Regions, Identical Twins, Invariant Moment, Pseudo-Zernike Moment

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PREDICTION OF LUNG CANCER USING IMAGE PROCESSING TECHNIQUES: A REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Prediction of lung cancer is most challenging problem due to structure of cancer cell, where most of the cells are overlapped each other. The image processing techniques are mostly used for prediction of lung cancer and also for early detection and treatment to prevent the lung cancer. To predict the lung cancer various features are extracted from the images therefore, pattern recognition based approaches are useful to predict the lung cancer. Here, a comprehensive review for the prediction of lung cancer by previous researcher using image processing techniques is presented. The summary for the prediction of lung cancer by previous researcher using image processing techniques is also presented.

KEYWORDS:

Classification, lung cancer, accuracy, image processing techniques

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A NEW DECISION TREE METHOD FOR DATA MINING IN MEDICINE

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ABSTRACT

Today, enormous amount of data is collected in medical databases. These databases may contain valuable information encapsulated in nontrivial relationships among symptoms and diagnoses. Extracting such dependencies from historical data is much easier to done by using medical systems. Such knowledge can be used in future medical decision making. In this paper, a new algorithm based on C4.5 to mine data for medicine applications proposed and then it is evaluated against two datasets and C4.5 algorithm in terms of accuracy.

KEYWORDS

Data mining, Medicine, Classification, Decision Tree, ID3, C4.5

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TEXT MINING: OPEN SOURCE TOKENIZATION TOOLS – AN ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

Text mining is the process of extracting interesting and non-trivial knowledge or information from unstructured text data. Text mining is the multidisciplinary field which draws on data mining, machine learning, information retrieval, computational linguistics and statistics. Important text mining processes are information extraction, information retrieval, natural language processing, text classification, content analysis and text clustering. All these processes are required to complete the preprocessing step before doing their intended task. Pre-processing significantly reduces the size of the input text documents and the actions involved in this step are sentence boundary determination, natural language specific stop-word elimination, tokenization and stemming. Among this, the most essential and important action is the tokenization. Tokenization helps to divide the textual information into individual words. For performing tokenization process, there are many open source tools are available. The main objective of this work is to analyze the performance of the seven open source tokenization tools. For this comparative analysis, we have taken Nlpdotnet Tokenizer, Mila Tokenizer, NLTK Word Tokenize, TextBlob Word Tokenize, MBSP Word Tokenize, Pattern Word Tokenize and Word Tokenization with Python NLTK. Based on the results, we observed that the Nlpdotnet Tokenizer tool performance is better than other tools.

KEYWORDS:

Text Mining, Preprocessing, Tokenization, machine learning, NLP

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WEB SPAM CLASSIFICATION USING SUPERVISED ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORK ALGORITHMS

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ABSTRACT

Due to the rapid growth in technology employed by the spammers, there is a need of classifiers that are more efficient, generic and highly adaptive. Neural Network based technologies have high ability of adaption as well as generalization. As per our knowledge, very little work has been done in this field using neural network. We present this paper to fill this gap. This paper evaluates performance of three supervised learning algorithms of artificial neural network by creating classifiers for the complex problem of latest web spam pattern classification. These algorithms are Conjugate Gradient algorithm, Resilient Backpropagation learning, and Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm.

KEYWORDS

Web spam, artificial neural network, back-propagation algorithms, Conjugate Gradient, Resilient Backpropagation, Levenberg-Marquardt, Web spam classification

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